
The Theme of Motherhood In Edna O'Brien's *The Country Girls*

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Abstract:

Motherhood is one of the main themes of Edna O'Brien's novels. She has depicted her characters from their childhood, and in that phase of life, the mother plays a vital role in the formation of their children. O'Brien has shown the girl children in many of her fictional works. She has crafted how the formation of a girl child becomes a woman by their upbringing in a patriarchal social setup, inadequacy of higher education, subordinate position in broken families, and the bad and fearful influence of their alcoholic, abusive fathers. In such a weak social structure, her protagonist feels lonely and loveless human beings. They dare to fight with their counterparts, but at the same time, their rigid patriarchal tradition leaves them alone and helpless. The author O'Brien has raised her voice to feel these female characters and their silent suffering throughout her work. She is recognised as the first woman writer from Ireland who has taken the charge to make her female characters express themselves and tried to take some actions to respond injustice that happened to them. In her early novels, O'Brien has focused on the girl children, where she has proven that the image of a woman depends on her upbringing in her childhood phase.

Keywords: Theme, Motherhood, Edna O'Brien

Introduction:

Edna O'Brien was one of the prolific women authors from Ireland. She has authored more than seventeen novels, six short story collections, as well as published poetry, children's books, stage-plays, television plays, screenplays, newspaper editorials, a personal memoir, and a biography of James Joyce. Rebecca Pelan, an Irish scholar, states that O'Brien "remains unchallenged as the most widely-published and distributed Irish woman writer of the modern period" (Stage-Irish 67).

She was the first woman author to give voice to the problems of Irish women from a patriarchal society. Her novels deal with young women protagonists. The prominent themes of her novels are love, loss, loneliness, domestic abuse, abortion, suicide, alcoholism, sexual assault, and incest. She has portrayed women characters in such a way that her protagonists remain in the memory of her readers. She has created real-life women characters, with all the folds of life. Her women were in the plight of social, political as well and cultural chains of an Irish society. Her characters show all the roles which is going to play by a woman plays in her life, from childhood to motherhood and simultaneously a womanhood.

It is observed that O'Brien is the first author who has depicted the actual bond of the mother-daughter relationship. Her first novel, *The Country Girls* (1960), tells the story of two

young girls – Caithleen Brady – “Kate” and Bridget Brennan – “Baba” from rural Irish society. They both are of the age of twelve years old and are shown as friends with each other.

While crafting these characters, O’Brien described minutely the bond between mothers and daughters. Mother is called the creator of the world. She gives birth to the child and nurtures it, so the mother is the first person in any child’s life who influences them the most. The aim of the present paper is to show how mothers are influencing their children, especially girl children, in the Irish patriarchal society.

It is seen that though women play an important part in any society, they are treated as secondary and subordinate to men in society. Women do not have any rights but have to do all the responsibilities of the family, and create the social setup of any community. The same is observed in the Irish society of the 1940s. O’Brien’s *The Country Girls* talks about the different phases of a woman’s life from girlhood to motherhood and womanhood. All these phases are interdependent. Through this novel, O’Brien broadens the silence on sexual matters and social and religious issues in traditional Irish society. This novel was not welcomed by the people and was banned by the Irish Censorship Board.

Motherhood: The Traditional Role of Mothers:

O’Brien’s *The Country Girls* is the story of two young protagonists who reflect the rural Irish Catholic family, where women were considered and characterized by emotional, physical, and sexual abuse. The author focuses on the social, cultural, and religious factors that become the causes of instability and dependency of women in the rural Irish families. The ideal image of a woman is to be a Mother. The first and initial identity of the woman in the Irish social setup is a mother, which is assigned by the state through the constitution and the religion through the Church. The mother characters of the novel, ‘*The Country Girls*’, have explored the characteristics of this identity. In ‘*The Country Girls*’, O’Brien has given two different pictures of mothers, first Cate’s mother and the other is Baba’s mother. Both mothers are representing the traditional as well as the new rebellious images of women. One accepts her motherhood silently and suffers a lot. The other one accepts motherhood in a very revolutionary way by defeating her family and children. One common thing they both share is that they are helpless and caught in their circumstances.

Mothers as Housewives:

According to Jenny Beale’s ‘Comparative study of the transition between the older rural and the modern urban generation women’ focuses on how the various opinions of women from one family, as a mother and as a daughter, differ due to the different social environments. It makes the point clear that daughters may not be like their mothers. J. Beale states that the traditional Irish mothers were allowed to be housewives; they did not have any options. Even after their marriages, they were opposed to working outside of home. She tells that, “only one in fifteen married women worked outside the home and women’s traditional roles as family-based wives and mothers were more firmly established”. This rule was made by the Irish state only after the independence of the republic, the state defined the role of women in Irish society.

The ideology adopted by the new State as a symbol of national unity was Catholic and nationalist. It was an ideology that glorified rural Irish life and romanticised the Catholic family. The problem for women was that this family was rigidly defined and patriarchal. The only roles for women were as wives and mothers; women were denied economic independence, discouraged from taking employment, and had very limited rights. (J. Beale)

O'Brien has crafted her mother's characters in such a way that they represent their contemporary socio-cultural pictures. They do not have their own identity. In *The Country Girls*, Caitlin's mother was not even referred to by her name, and she was called Mama only throughout the novel.

Silent Sufferers:

O'Brien pictured a rural village in Ireland, where the family of Caithleen lives on a small farm. Caithleen described her mother as a housewife and a farmer. Her mother knows their financial shortcomings described by Kate's narration. She says, "In our house, things were either broken or not used at all. Mama had new clippers and several coils of rope in a wardrobe upstairs; she said they'd only get broken or stolen if she brought them down." (TCG 95). This expression shows the sacrifice of her mother to manage the lifestyle that was expected of them (TCG 96). Kate narrates her mother as one of the best mothers in the world. She loves her very much. Her mother is the only moral support to her, because it is shown in the beginning of the novel that Kate has a fear of her father, who is an alcoholic addict, abusive, irresponsible, and a loveless person. He returns home too late, drunk, and shouts at her mother. She silently faces every abuse by him because of the patriarchal social setup. Women have to follow their husbands without any opposition, whether they like it or not. She was made to remain silent. She represents the whole race of women who become the victims of their wrong marriages, and due to the social restrictions on women, they were not allowed to leave their husbands. Divorce was not permitted, so they had to remain voiceless.

Conclusion:

Thus, the above discussion will focus on the plight of women as housewives and mothers. Women have to accept both roles without their choice, helplessly. They would be the example of happy wives and mothers, but they are not due to the patriarchal social setup. Therefore, they remain subordinate, dependent, alone, and helpless mothers as well as wives. As a result, as a mother, they couldn't make their children, especially daughters to think independently and feel free. O'Brien depicted the real picture of Irish women.

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